

Constituents of *Argemone* species

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Manuscript received 18 February 2010, revised 04 June 2010, accepted 14 June 2010

Abstract : The flavones, quercetin and rutin, and the alkaloid 1-tetrahydrocoptisine have been isolated respectively from the whole plant of *Argemone mexicana* and *Argemone ochroleuca*. Their structures have been established by various spectral data. This is the first report of occurrence of quercetin and rutin in *A. mexicana* and 1-tetrahydrocoptisine in *A. ochroleuca*.

Keywords : *Argemone mexicana*, *Argemone ochroleuca*, Papaveraceae, quercetin, rutin, 1-tetrahydrocoptisine.

Introduction

Argemone mexicana Linn., a native plant of Mexico is an erect prickly annual herb with yellow flowers naturalized throughout India. It is used in Indian medicine for the treatment of fever, diarrhoea and dysentery¹. Some of the isolated alkaloids have shown anti-HIV², anti-cancer³ and hepatotoxic⁴ activities. The seed oil causes high tension glaucoma, dropsy, anemia and breathlessness due to presence of alkaloids, sanguinarine and dihydrosanguinarine⁵. Earlier chemical investigations of this plant has revealed the presence of many alkaloids^{2,3,6-10}, phenolics¹¹ and amino acids¹². *A. ochroleuca* Sweet is similar to *A. mexicana* but with white flowers and is widely distributed in Punjab, Haryana and Uttar Pradesh. The plant appears to have similar medicinal properties as *A. mexicana*¹. A number of fatty acids, amino acids, flavonoids and alkaloids have earlier been reported¹³⁻¹⁶. The present study deals with the isolation of further constituents from the above two species. The flavones, quercetin and rutin have been isolated from *A. mexicana* and 1-tetrahydrocoptisine from *A. ochroleuca*. This is the first report of the isolation of these compounds from respective species.

Results and discussion

Chromatographic resolution of methanolic extract of *A. mexicana* furnished flavonoids quercetin (1)¹⁷ and rutin (2)¹⁷ whereas the crude base fraction of methanolic

extract of *A. ochroleuca* on chromatography yielded isoquinoline alkaloid, 1-tetrahydrocoptisine (3)¹⁸. These compounds were identified by direct comparison of their physical and spectral data with literature values and direct comparison with authentic samples.

Experimental

Plant material : The whole plant of *A. mexicana* and *A. ochroleuca* were collected from Banaras Hindu University Campus, Varanasi, India and identified by Prof. N. K. Dubey, Department of Botany, Banaras Hindu University. Specimen samples are kept in the department.

Extraction and isolation : Dried whole plant (3 kg) of *A. mexicana* was powdered and repeatedly extracted with MeOH (15 L) by percolation at room temperature. The methanol extract (300 g) was chromatographed over SiO₂ gel column, eluted with solvents of increasing polarity. The eluates from CHCl₃-MeOH (4 : 1) after crystallization from MeOH furnished quercetin (1) (26 mg) as yellow granules, m.p. 180–182 °C, C₂₁H₂₀O₁₁ (HRMS, *m/z* 448.1010 (M⁺), calcd. for 448.1005). It exhibited in its ¹H NMR spectrum (DMSO-*d*₆) five aromatic hydrogens (δ 6.20, 6.40, 6.90, 7.25, 7.30), four phenolic hydroxyl protons (δ 9.38, 9.70, 10.80, 12.60) and eleven rhamnosyl protons (δ 0.80, 3.10–4.90, 5.28). Crystallization of the eluates from CHCl₃-MeOH (1 : 1) yielded rutin (2) (28 mg) as light yellow granules, m.p. 188–190 °C, C₂₇H₃₀O₁₆ (HRMS, *m/z* 610.1540 (M⁺), calcd. for

610.1533). It exhibited in its ^1H NMR spectrum ($\text{DMSO-}d_6$) five aromatic protons (δ 6.20, 6.40, 8.92, 7.25, 7.30), four phenolic hydroxyl protons (δ 9.19, 9.68, 10.84, 12.59) and twenty one glucosyl and rhamnosyl protons (δ 0.97, 3.02–4.60, 5.10, 5.33). Hydrolysis of compounds **1** and **2** furnished quercetin (m.m.p. and co-TLC). The sugar residue in **1** was identified as rhamnose, and in **2** as rhamnose and glucose (co-PC).

Dried whole plant of *A. ochroleuca* (2 kg) was powdered and repeatedly extracted with MeOH (10 L) by percolation at room temperature. On removal of solvent, the methanolic extract afforded a brown gummy mass (200 g) which was stirred mechanically with 7% aqueous citric acid. The aqueous acidic solution was separated and basified with ammonium hydroxide and extracted several times with CHCl_3 (2 L). The combined CHCl_3 extract on evaporation furnished a mixture of crude bases (12 g). The crude base fraction was chromatographed over SiO_2 gel column and the eluates from $\text{C}_6\text{H}_6\text{-CHCl}_3$ (1 : 1) was collected, which on crystallization from MeOH gave 1-tetrahydrocoptisine (**3**) (28 mg) as colorless needles, m.p. 200–202 °C, $[\alpha]^{20}_{\text{D}} -339^\circ$ (*c*, 0.31 CHCl_3), $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{17}\text{NO}_4$ (HRMS, *m/z* 323.1160 (M^+), calcd. for 323.1157). It exhibited in its ^1H MMR spectrum (CDCl_3) four aromatic protons (δ 5.92, 6.60, 6.64, 6.65), two methylenedioxy protons (δ 5.89, 5.92), four methylenes and a methine protons (δ 2.64–4.07).

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